

Living Stigma- Issues and Concerns with Special reference to Transgender Community

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ABSTRACT

People are associated with specific gender based on their genitals. Transgenders feel a mismatch in their gender and associate to the traits of opposite gender gradually. There are broad spectrum of people who gradually identify themselves with gender different to which they are born. Traditionally transgenders are of divine creature but gradually they have been marginalized substantially. Their life is highly influenced through culture, tradition and practices. They are known as 'third gender' who are exposed to the evils of social stigma and discrimination. Due to lack of skills and social rejection this segment chooses prostitution or beggary as a means for their life. Substantial population of transgenders lives social exclusion and vulnerability to communicable diseases. In the modern society discrimination and violence based on race, gender, income, ethnicity, sexual identity has become a global concern seeking immediate action. In this direction this study gains momentum to find ways forward. This is an exploratory study with secondary data. It exposes about the issues of transgenders pertaining to social exclusion, rejection, stigma, gender crisis and lack of protection

Key Words: Gender, Identity, Transgenders, Third Gender, Sexual Minority

1. INTRODUCTION:

Transgenders were divine traditionally but marginalized substantially [1]. The people who associate with the gender to which they have not born with nonconformity to which they are born. They comprise of 'female-to-male' and 'male-to-female' consisting of draggers, cross dressers, queers etc. They called as 'zenanas', 'shikandies', 'metis', 'kinner', 'Chakka', 'Aravani', 'Jogta' etc. Ramayana, Veda and Purana specify on third gender. The sex is determined based on the reproductive system. It depicts the societal roles [2]. According to Diagnostic and Statistical Manual 4 one among 30,000 boys and 10000 females suffer gender identity disorder or 'Gender Dysphoria' [3]. In India 70 million are lesbians, gay and transgenders. Census Report 2011 depict about 4.88 lakh transgenders in India. UP possess (28.18 per cent) adults, children between 0-6 years (34.15 per cent), Scheduled Caste (33.50 per cent) respectively [4]. It is descriptive study on gender identity crisis to live the gender of choice with secondary data [5]. High death rate among transgender due to unlawful hormone use without assistance from the specialist resulting in strokes, coronary episodes, silicone infusions and vein apoplexy. Hijras are highly HIV infectious as per the study conducted in Mumbai found with Serop (68 per cent) and syphilis (57 per cent). They are exposed to discrimination, harassment, verbal abuse, violence, arrest, rejection, desertion, no share in property [7]. The anti-transgender stigma causes violence [8]. Atrocities by police is proved in Jayalakshmi vs The State of Tamil Nadu. These cause depression, self-destruction, cultural shame, and stress. They practice 'Castration' or Sex Reassignment Surgery (SRS) which is traumatic. Many who have not mutilated prefer sex with men. Problems in using washroom in public places. Offences committed by normal were misrepresented as offences committed by the transgenders. Sexual reorientation is better among male to female category [10]. To understand the legal regime affecting transgenders in India, Constitution itself guarantees equality, right to freedom, prohibits discrimination. In 2014, India's Supreme Court in Nalsa Judgement [11] held that Right to Life is a part of Article 21 and confirmed them as people from 'Third Gender'. The Election Commission issued direction to enroll transgenders as third gender. Several laws such as Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act, 1986, Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013, Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005, Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2015, Protection of Child Rights Act, 2005, Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act, 2012, Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act, 1989 will be applicable. IPC declares abandonment of child as punishable offence under Section 317. In Navtej Singh Johar v. Union of India [12], apex court issued landmark judgment for LGBT by making section 377 of IPC unconstitutional.

2. ISSUES CONCERNING THE TRANSGENDER COMMUNITY:

Transgenders are affected with high mortality rate even though they are not reporting the deaths. Most of the deaths are due to illegal hormone usage without seeking experts advice. They are highly prone to sexually transmitted diseases including HIV where almost 17.5 per cent are HIV positive and 72 per cent with STI (48 per cent with HSV-1, 29 per cent with HSV-2 and 7.8 per cent with HBV respectively) [6]. Most of them are victimized to discrimination, harassment, abuse, violence, arrest, desertion. Anti-transgender stigma has lead to the culture of violence [8]. It is verdict to produce false media reports. Psychological problems such as bullying, rejection, non affiliation, abuse, comments and verbal attacks cause distress, suicide and self harm. Hormonal treatment and Sex Reassignment Surgeries are traumatic hence do not go for it but have sex with men. Studies on outlook concern of transgenders reported about diet practices among male to female segment. Usage of public washrooms in public places has been a problem. Criminal acts are entrusted upon transgenders to protect themselves. The transgenders begging are victimized to police atrocities, harm, harassment, fake cases etc.

3. OBSERVATION AND DISCUSSION:

It is found that societal stigma is causing suicide of transsexuals [13]. Organization working for transgenders is unevenly distributed in the country hence seeks regional priority [14]. Death and Violence is not reported [15]. Sentinel Surveillance Report of NACO report high HIV rate [16]. They need better therapeutic interventions [17]. 5 transgenders contested for Lok Sabha election of 2019. They shall be benefitted with MGNREGP and National Rural Livelihood Mission [18]. Gender differences are observed in schools [19]. Welfare Schemes of the government on education, social assistance, health care, employment need to be extended. Atrocities need to be curbed with penalty. Grant of land with loan and subsidies, housing, education, rehabilitation of prostitution and beggary and protection from sexual harassment will help. Council at national level need to be formed. Proper HR Policies shall be developed [20]. Collaborative efforts can only find a solution [21]. Constitution of welfare boards for transgenders and constituting separate wards in the government hospitals will also help in this regard.

4. WAYS FOR WARD:

The creation of identity to the transgenders is the primary concern. Welfare Schemes on education, social assistance, health, employment are the need. Atrocities including abuse, violence, discrimination need to be punished. Grant of government lands on proven good work along with loan facility can yield entrepreneurial outcome. Consideration for housing under Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana would be beneficial. Rehabilitation from prostitution and beggary are essential. Institutions for sexual minorities will be beneficial in nation building. The Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act 2013 need to be extended to transgenders. National Council for Transgenders shall be constituted. Reform HR Policies with favorable approaches towards third gender. Sensitization of trade unions about transgender issues and concerns. Grant of political rights, special police cells, sensitization on Sex Reassignment Surgery (SRS), legal aid. Empowerment strategies with multifaceted areas is essential to main stream them. Gender Resource Centers shall maintain the data base of transgenders in the village levels. Under New Education Policy 2020 states should envisage special provisions for the sexual minorities. Central schemes on scholarship and fellowship need to be introduced. Welfare Board to protect them against contingencies of life. Separate wards for transgenders in General Hospital will help in delivering health services better. The higher education and research institutions shall create public platforms by organizing campaigns, workshops, seminars, conferences and facilitate research and deliberations on the transgender issues will be of greater impact. Tagging transgender welfare as an element of Corporate Social Responsibility would be a great idea in handling the concerns of third gender. There is a need to bring the transgender within the ambit of present schemes on social insurance with respect to old age pension (Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension scheme), Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana, Jan Dhan Yojana, Ayushman Bharath, MUDRA, Atal Pension Yojana, PM Jeevan Jyothi Bima Yojana, National Health Mission, Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, National Policy on Skill Development, 2009 etc.

5. CONCLUSION:

Transsexuals have equal right to live in this world. Human Rights of the transgenders shall be protected. The third gender sensitive moves including issue of identity cards, housing, voting rights, contesting for election, schemes, facilities, legal etc. are important [22]. Inclusive growth of sexual minorities is required to mainstream them [23]. Eliminate the stigma in the society on transgenders through collective partnership of the government, people, service organisation, bureaucrats etc. [24]. The impact of technology may bring universal acceptance to transgender community [25]. Work culture with special concern for the transgenders in the industrial employment adding value to the Gross Domestic Product. Gender Identity Disorder need to be educated and sensitized. All are free to live the gender of their choice as a human right. Granting government lands with loan, subsidy would start many new entrepreneurial journeys. Enactment of gender sensitive legislations, public policies, schemes, redressal mechanisms, inclusive strategies, support system, financial packages, grant in aids, schemes and programmes need to be focused much. Involving transgenders in the society in general and is a big task in the modern society but if it happens it would create an history in the evolutionary phase of the country [26]. Let us see how we all can contribute ourselves to this noble cause.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Kalra, G. (2012). Hijras: The unique transgender culture of India. *International Journal of Culture and Mental Health*, 5(2), 121-126.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [2] Human Rights Campaign (HRC). (2004). What does 'transgender' mean? Retrieved from http://www.hrc.org/Template.cfm?Section=Coming_Out_as_Transgender&Template=/ContentManagement/ContentDisplay.cfm&ContentID=21795 on 24th September, 2021
- [3] Guha, M. (2014). Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders: DSM- 5, *Reference Reviews*.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [4] Retrieved from <http://www.census2011.co.in/transgender.php>. on 4th October, 2021
- [5] Pradeep, M. D. (2018). Philosophical Review on the Basic & Action Research Methods-A Critical Analysis, *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, ISSN: 2581-6012, 3(2), 120-129.
[Google ScholarCrossRef](#)
- [6] Shinde S Setia MS, Row –Kavi A. et al. Male sex workers are we ignoring a risk group in Mumbai, India. *Indian J Dermatol Venereol Leprol*: 75(1): 41-46
[Google Scholar](#)
- [7] Neeraj, M. K., & Sreenath Muraleedharan, K. (2021). Tracing the Position of Lgbt Community with in the Indian Context. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 25(6), 9129-9137.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [8] Moran, L. J., & Sharpe, A. N. (2004). Violence, identity and policing: The case of violence against transgender people. *Criminal justice*, 4(4), 395-417.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [9] Laura Amata. Laura's Playground Transgender suicide Report, Retrieved from www.search.lauras-playground.com on 4th October, 2021
- [10] Blanchard, R., Clemmensen, L. H., & Steiner, B. W. (1983). Gender reorientation and psychosocial adjustment in male-to-female transsexuals. *Archives of sexual behavior*, 12(6), 503-509.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [11] Radhakrishnan, K. S. (2020). In the supreme court of India Civil original jurisdiction Writ petition (Civil) No. 400 of 2012 National legal services authority. Judgment 2013.
[Google Scholar](#)

- [12] McDonald-Norman, D. (2018). Prohibition of same-sex sexual conduct struck down in India. *Bar News: The Journal of the NSW Bar Association*, (Summer 2018), 78-79.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [13] Gleason, H. A., Livingston, N. A., Peters, M. M., Oost, K. M., Reely, E., & Cochran, B. N. (2016). Effects of state nondiscrimination laws on transgender and gender-nonconforming individuals' perceived community stigma and mental health. *Journal of Gay & Lesbian Mental Health*, 20(4), 350-362.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [14] Chakrapani, V., Newman, P. A., Mhaprolkar, H., & Kavi, A. R. (2007). Sexual and social networks of MSM and Hijras in India: a qualitative study. *The Humsafar Trust, Mumbai. Report presented to the National AIDS Control Organization, India.*
[Google Scholar](#)
- [15] Balarajan, Y., Selvaraj, S., & Subramanian, S. V. (2011). Health care and equity in India. *The Lancet*, 377(9764), 505-515.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [16] Biswas, S., Chakraborty, D., Ghosh, P., Kumar, P., Adhikary, R., & Saha, M. K. (2020). HIV Risk profile and its socio-demographic correlates among long-distance truckers in West Bengal, India: Evidence from national HIV sentinel surveillance 2017. *Indian journal of public health*, 64(5), 8.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [17] Midence, K., & Hargreaves, I. (1997). Psychosocial adjustment in male-to-female transsexuals: An overview of the research evidence. *The Journal of psychology*, 131(6), 602-614.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [18] Planning Commission. (2013). Twelfth Five Year Plan, 2012-7, Economic Sectors, Volume II.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [19] Nevatia, S., Raj, Mahajan, S., Shah, C., & Lesbians and Bisexuals in Action (LABIA). (2012). Bound by norms and out of bounds: Experiences of PAGFB (Persons assigned gender female at birth) within the formal education system: Lesbians and bisexuals in action (LABIA). *Contemporary Education Dialogue*, 9(2), 173-196.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [20] Davis, D. (2009). Transgender issues in the workplace: HRD's newest challenge/opportunity. *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, 11(1), 109-120.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [21] Chakrapani, V., Newman, P. A., & Noronha, E. (2018). Hijras/transwomen and sex work in India. *Transgender sex work and society*, 214-235.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [22] Sawant, N. S. (2017). Transgender: status in India. *Annals of Indian Psychiatry*, 1(2), 59.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [23] Pradeep, M.D., & Kalicharan, M. (2016). Life Centric Skill Enrichment Framework—An Effective Pedagogy for Empowerment. *International Journal of Computational Research and Development (IJCRD)*, 1, 40-46.
[Google Scholar](#)[CrossRef](#)
- [24] Pradeep, M. D. (2018). Study on the Mobility in Status of Women Evolutionary Phases towards Empowerment in India. *International Journal of Management, Technology and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 3(2), 73-86.
[Google Scholar](#)[CrossRef](#)
- [25] Vocks, S., Stahn, C., Loenser, K., & Legenbauer, T. (2009). Eating and body image disturbances in male-to-female and female-to-male transsexuals. *Archives of sexual behavior*, 38(3), 364-377.